

DEFORMATION ON COPPER MATRIX ON THERMAL

CYCLING A COPPER/STEEL UNIT COMPOSITE

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Composite materials may suffer extensive damage under varying temperature conditions due to thermal stresses generated because of the difference in expansion coefficients of the two components. A metallographic study has been made of a fiber composite consisting of a steel wire enclosed by a shell of copper when subjected to thermal cycling. The copper matrix accommodated thermal stresses generated by means of slip at low temperatures. On cycling to a peak temperature between $0.2T_m$ and $0.5T_m$, grain boundary sliding caused cavitation at triple points. Little grain boundary migration was observed in this range; the impurities in copper matrix having pinned the boundaries. On cycling to temperatures $> 0.5T_m$, extensive boundary migration but lesser sliding was observed. At these temperatures, the impurities had diffused away from the boundaries and the latter could migrate under the action of thermal stresses and thereby relieve them. Recovery phenomena, like grain boundary migration and annealing twins, above $0.5T_m$ led to a reduction in boundary sliding and suppressed the tendency for intergranular cracking in the matrix due to thermal stresses.

Introduction

Important advances have been made in the last decade or so in obtaining an understanding of the behavior of composite materials. An important question with regard to their application in conditions involving high and varying temperature conditions is the behavior of the soft matrix component under these circumstances. The question is of considerable importance because the composite materials are by definition heterogeneous materials and thus the mismatch in the coefficient of expansion of the components will give rise to thermal stresses of considerable magnitude even in conditions involving uniform temperature distribution in the composite (1). A unit composite consisting of a single steel fiber in copper matrix was used in this study to examine the deformation behavior of the copper matrix when the composite undergoes cyclic temperature variations.

Experimental

Composite specimens (10 mm long) were cut from a 2 mm diameter copper/steel bimetallic wire consisting of electrolytic grade copper coating around an SAE 1032 steel core. The steel core diameter was 1.6 mm. The composite was fabricated, as per manufacturer's[†] description, by pouring liquid copper in a heated mold containing the steel core. The final size and shape of the as received wire were obtained by hot rolling and drawing.

For cycling, the specimens were vacuum encapsulated in quartz capsules and heated slowly in a furnace to the peak temperature (200, 300, 400, 500, 600 and 700°C), held at the peak temperature for 15 minutes and then quenched in water. The specimens were examined in optical and scanning electron microscopes for studying the microstructural changes occurring during the thermal cycling.

Results

The polished surface of a transverse section of the composite is shown in Fig. 1. The copper surface (marked Cu in figure) is smooth and slip line free. Thermal stresses are generated in both steel and copper on cycling. However, it is the softer component i.e. copper here which accommodates and, thus, leads to a relaxation

[†]Copperweld Industries International, Inc., New York

of the thermal stresses. The steel core experiences only elastic deformation and hence no microstructural changes occur in it on cycling. Before the elastic thermal stresses in the steel core can reach its yield point, the copper matrix deforms plastically by slip at low temperatures and by grain boundary sliding/migration and cavitation at high temperatures. We shall, therefore, focus our attention on what goes on in the copper shell that surrounds the steel core.

Fig. 2 shows a transverse section of the composite after 3 cycles between 200°C and 25°C. Grain boundaries have become delineated due to the thermal etching action and slip lines have appeared. On cycling to 400°C, voids mainly at and around the grain boundary triple points started appearing after 3-5 cycles. Fig. 3, which is a scanning electron micrograph of a sample cycled 10 times between 400 and 25°C, shows the voids formed at triple points. Some growth of voids also appears to have occurred. The incidence of voids at the grain boundary triple points increased with increasing peak temperature. Grain boundary sliding, void growth and coalescence leading to the formation of grain face cracks occurred. This can be seen in Fig. 4 which is a scanning micrograph of a sample that has been cycled 10 times between 500 and 25°C. Notice the concentration of slip lines in the vicinity of the grain boundaries. There is also a hint of grain boundary migration. The latter phenomenon became very prominent on cycling to 600°C and above. One should remark here that voids were concentrated on grain boundaries near the interface although no distinction could be made as to their distribution along radial and/or transverse boundaries. On cycling to 600°C and above, grain boundary migration was observed to occur extensively while at the same time grain boundary sliding and cavitation occurred less frequently. An extreme case of this is shown in Figs. 5(a) and 5(b) which are from a sample cycled 12 times between 700 and 25°C. Fig. 5(a) is a scanning micrograph under compositional contrast using a solid pair detector. In this mode of SEM operation, the contrast due to compositional differences is enhanced. Notice the agglomeration of impurities away from the grain boundaries and the grain growth that has occurred due to the migrating grain boundaries. Fig. 5(b) shows the same area as in 5(a) but using the topographical contrast mode wherein the contrast due to topography is enhanced. Observe the slip markings in the grain bodies which are barely visible in 5(a). On the other hand, the agglomerated impurities cannot be distinguished in 5(b). Cavitation did occur in this case but after 20 cycles. Figs. 6(a) and 6(b) show r-type

voids formed in copper on cycling 20 times to 700°. Fig. 6(b) is a magnified area of Fig. 6(a). Once the cavities were nucleated, their growth and coalescence to form intercrystalline cracks occurred in 2-3 cycles.

Some samples were repolished after cycling and examined in the microscope. The ones cycled to peak temperatures of 500°C and above showed annealing twins. Fig. 7 shows this for a sample cycled 6 times between 600 and 250°C. Notice that voids did not form at twin boundaries. A few samples were sectioned longitudinally and polished. No appreciable difference in the microstructure existed between the longitudinal and transverse sections.

Discussion

On subjecting composite materials to thermal cycling, thermal stresses which are proportional to the amplitude of the thermal cycle, ΔT , and to the difference in the coefficients of expansion of fiber and matrix, $\Delta\alpha$, arise. The thermal stresses arise in both the components. However, the softer component of the two gives way plastically and thermal stresses are largely relaxed. This accommodation on the part of the softer component (generally, the matrix) may involve considerable microstructural damage to it, as has been amply demonstrated in earlier work (1-3). It is worth reiterating here that composite materials are inherently heterogeneous and as such thermal stresses having origin in expansion coefficient mismatch of the components cannot be eliminated entirely. The conventional stress-relief-anneal treatment can, at best, attempt to minimize them.

The composite used in the present work is a model composite in that the steel fiber has a small shell of copper matrix and thus, would represent a high fiber volume fraction composite wherein the matrix volume associated with each fiber is small. In this work, the steel fiber has a volume fraction of 0.64 of the composite. If one puts in the relevant numbers for the two components in the expressions for the thermal stresses (4,1) for such a unit composite and plots the principal elastic thermal stresses and the effective stresses due to Tresca and von Mises criteria in matrix vs. distance in the matrix, one gets the plot shown in Fig. 8. Notice that the plot is for heating leading to a $\Delta T = 1^\circ\text{C}$. σ_r goes to zero at the surface of the copper matrix shell. This follows from the boundary condition that a free surface cannot support a normal stress. Note also that unlike the low V_f composite case (1,2) where the matrix shell is fairly

thick, σ_z is not insignificant. Both σ_θ and σ_r are appreciable only near the fiber matrix interface. For work hardened, electrolytic grade copper, a reasonable estimate of yield stress is 200 MN/m^2 (5) which means that a $\Delta T = 200^\circ\text{C}$ is required to make it yield in the very first cycle. In practice the amplitude of thermal cycle, ΔT , required to make it yield will be much less than that because the yield strength decreases with increasing temperature. However, as the copper matrix yields and starts deforming plastically it undergoes work hardening. Above a certain temperature, thermal stresses will also be reduced by recovery processes in the matrix (1,3). Thus, in each cycle there occurs plastic deformation by slip in the lower part of the thermal cycle and some kind of stress relaxation and creep deformation in the high temperature part of the cycle.

On cycling to peak temperatures of $200\text{-}300^\circ\text{C}$, only plastic deformation, as manifested by the appearance of slip lines, of copper matrix occurred (Fig. 2). No gross manifestation of creep was observed. On cycling to 400°C , voids at grain boundary triple points started appearing. These voids at or around the triple points predominated upto about 500°C . Above this temperature voids at the grain boundaries were observed. The voids formed at the grain boundary triple points are commonly referred to as w-type while the voids formed at grain boundaries but away from the triple points are referred to as r-type voids (6). It is well known (7,8) that w-type cavities form in high stress, low temperature creep while r-type cavities form in low stress, high temperature creep tests. It would appear that the copper matrix is in the former state upto $400\text{-}500^\circ\text{C}$ wherein comparatively higher thermal stresses that develop lead to grain boundary triple point void formation by grain boundary sliding as per Zener's mechanism (9). Above 500°C , r-type voids are observed because at such high temperature, small magnitude thermal stresses develop as there occur recovery phenomena (see below) and r-type cavities start forming due to grain boundary sliding as per mechanisms proposed by many workers (10,11). A general feature of the cavity formation was a higher concentration of them near the fiber matrix interface which is understandable in that thermal stresses generated are higher near the interface.

Little grain boundary migration was observed upto 500°C . Above this temperature, the impurities, presumably oxides, in the copper matrix had coarsened and diffused away from the grain boundaries (see Fig. 5) and one could observe grain boundary migration. Along with

the incidence of grain boundary migration, there occurred a decrease in the boundary sliding and cavitation. As is well known (8,9,12) boundary migration extends creep ductility. Chen and Machlin (12) explained that migration destroyed the boundary jogs and thus prevented the nucleation of voids. It would appear that below 600°C, boundaries are pinned by the impurities and thus are prevented from migrating. Under these conditions, there occurs extensive grain boundary sliding and cavitation. While above 0.5T_m, the impurities have coarsened by dissolution of the smaller ones and growth of the larger ones and diffused away from the boundaries; leaving them free to migrate. Inasmuch as coarsening of impurities proceeds by diffusion of the impurity atoms through the copper matrix, it is understandable that this agglomeration occurred markedly at higher temperatures. Above 500°C, another recovery mechanism that occurred was that of the formation of annealing twins. Notice that no voids formed at twin boundaries which is eminently reasonable inasmuch as a twin interface is coherent and sliding at a twin boundary would be an unlikely mechanism of stress relaxation. As a general statement about the recovery taking place in the high temperature part of the thermal cycle, one can say that a part of the stored energy of plastic deformation in the lower temperature part of the thermal cycle is used up in the formation of annealing twins and another part of the stored energy of deformation acts as the driving force for the grain boundary migration.

With progressive cycling, the voids formed at the grain boundaries grew, coalesced and formed intercrystalline cracks. One should point out that such intercrystalline cracking did not appear on cycling upto 50 times to 200°C indicating the necessity of cycling to higher temperatures for its appearance. On cycling to 400°C and above, the grain boundary voids formed readily and once formed they seemed to grow and coalesce to form grain face cracks in a matter of 2-3 cycles. This growth of voids could occur by further grain boundary sliding and/or Nabarro-Herring creep. Excess vacancy concentration will result from both quenching from the peak temperature and plastic deformation and this could be helpful in void growth (2). The vacancy concentration increases exponentially with temperature. A quick estimate indicates that there is an order of magnitude increase in the vacancy concentration on raising the peak temperature from 500 to 700°C. The rather large vacancy concentration available above 400-500°C would promote grain boundary migration which ultimately involves atomic diffusion across the boundary. The number of cycles required

to initiate cavitation increased on cycling to peak temperatures above 500°C. Thus, cycling to peak temperatures $> 0.5T_m$ helped partially relax the thermal stresses in a harmless manner by boundary migration and formation of annealing twins which, in turn, led to a reduced incidence of boundary sliding and cavitation. However, once the cavities were nucleated, the recovery phenomena of grain boundary migration and annealing twins did not seem to affect very much their growth and ultimate intercrystalline crack formation.

Conclusions

Copper matrix deformed plastically by slip at low temperatures in response to the thermal stresses generated on thermal cycling of the composite. On cycling through $0.5T_m$, grain boundary sliding and cavitation at triple points occurred indicating the applicability of Zener mechanism of stress relaxation at the grain boundary. Little grain boundary migration was observed upto $0.5T_m$ as impurities pinned the boundaries against migration. On cycling to peak temperatures above $0.5T_m$, the impurities agglomerated away from the grain boundaries, leaving them free to migrate. With increasing peak cycling temperature, there occurred an increasing amount of grain boundary migration while concurrently grain boundary sliding and cavitation decreased. Cavitation did occur but after a larger number of cycles. Annealing twins also formed on cycling above $0.5T_m$. Thus, on cycling to peak temperatures above $0.5T_m$, recovery phenomena helped partially relax the thermal stresses in a harmless way leading to a delay in the onset of cavitation and intergranular cracking.

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Fig.1 - A scanning electron micrograph showing the polished transverse surface before thermal cycling. The copper surface is smooth and free of any slip lines or voids. 2000 X

Fig.2 - A scanning electron micrograph of a sample after 3 cycles (200-25°C). The grain boundaries have become delineated due to thermal etching and slip lines have appeared. 3000 X

Fig.3 - A scanning electron micrograph of a sample cycled 10 times (400-25°C) showing the void formation at grain boundary triple points. 2500 X

Fig.4 - Formation of grain face crack by void growth and coalescence. Notice also the slip in the vicinity of the grain boundaries. 10 cycles, 500-25°C. SEM. 500 X

Fig.5 - 12 cycles, 700-25°C. SEM. (a) Compositional contrast. Notice the agglomeration of impurities away from the grain boundaries and the grain growth due to the boundary migration.500X(b) Same area as that in (a) but under topographical contrast. Here the slip markings are visible. 500 X

Fig.6 - 20 cycles, 700-25°C. SEM. (a) r-type void formation. 1000 X (b) a higher mag. of a region of (a). 10.000 X

Fig.7 - A scanning electron micrograph showing the formation of annealing twins in a sample cycled 6 times between 600-25°C. Note the absence of voids at twin boundaries. 300 X

Fig.8 - Plot of thermal stresses induced in matrix, for heating of 1°C , i.e. $\Delta T = 1^\circ\text{C}$, versus distance in the matrix.